

LIQUID RENEWABLE ENERGY CARRIERS FROM
CAPTURED CARBON EMISSIONS

DELIVERABLE D1.2

Data Management Plan

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DISCLAIMER FOR METHODOLOGY

This project has used a standard methodology already developed in the REDOL project (grant agreement number: 101.091.668), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the grant agreement conditions for CAPTUS (grant agreement number: 101.118.265).

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Version	2

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public – fully open	X
SEN	Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

CHANGE CONTROL

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Data management is an important aspect of European projects because it guarantees long-term accessibility and preservation of data not only during the project, but also after the project finishes. The CAPTUS data management plan (based on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan template) explains the general procedures and minimum requirements that specific data management procedures in each work package, task, or organisation should be built upon. It is written with the consortium and a public audience in mind. This document includes: 1) Data set reference and name. 2) Data set descriptions, 3) Standards and metadata, 4) Data sharing, 5) Archiving and 6) The 'ethics requirements' that the project must comply with.

The Data Manage Plan (DMP) details what data CAPTUS will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved. It is expected that the DMP increases research efficiency, saves time and resources, enhances data security and minimizes the risk of data loss. DMP takes special care to make the data findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable according to FAIR guiding principles.

Moreover, guidelines, recommendations and useful information regarding the repositories, the strategies, and the management of the data following the FAIR principles are included in the document.

Finally, a specific explanation covering GDPR is included in this document to present how this data will be handled.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
AECs	Architects Engineers and Constructors
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Modelling
CDE	Common Data Environment
DBL	Digital Building Logbook
DM	Data Model
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPA	Data Protection Agreements
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DT	Digital Twin
DVL	Deliverable

DX.X	Project Deliverable with reference number
EC	European Commission
EII	Energy Intensive Industry
ESCO	Energy Service Company
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (in reference to data)
FM	Facility Manager
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
QA	Quality Assurance
UI	User Interfaces
WLC	Whole Life Carbon
WP	Work package
WT	Work task

1 INTRODUCTION

CAPTUS is an innovation action project that aims to demonstrate sustainable and cost-effective pathways to produce high-added value RECs in EIs by valorising industrial carbon emissions and integrating renewable electricity surplus. Three complete REC value chains will be demonstrated at 3 different demonstration sites:

1. Bioprocess based on a two-stage fermentation to produce triglycerides in a steel plant.
2. Lipids-rich microalgae cultivation followed by hydrothermal liquefaction to produce bio-oils in a chemical plant.
3. Electrochemical reduction of CO₂ to produce formic acid in a cement plant.

The proposed technologies will be tested and endorsed from lab to pilot scale, and the obtained RECs will be validated by upgrading studies for the formulation of high-performance fuels. In addition to developing, engineering and implementing CCU technologies along the 3 demo-sites, CAPTUS will analyse the integration of the validated solutions in EIs regarding economic, environmental, societal and geo-political criteria. By contributing with guidelines and strategies for the decarbonization roadmap, CAPTUS will improve awareness and acceptance of CCU technologies and the obtained RECs, as well as construct suitable business cases.

To cover this ambitious solution data collection, creation and management are needed during and after the proper project execution. The aim of this DMP is to present information regarding the different procedures. The DMP details what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved. It is expected that the DMP increases research efficiency, saves time and resources in the long run, enhances data security and minimizes the risk of data loss.

Important definitions followed in this document are:

- **Data** under the frame of the CAPTUS project should be understood as the needed inputs to create the software tools, models, apps, technologies (research outputs), and exploitable results of the project.
- **Research outputs** under the frame of the CAPTUS project should be understood as software, codes, workflows, protocols, models, algorithms, equipment and any other tentative result created by project partners.

CAPTUS project partners prepared this document at the beginning of the project (M1-M6). Since this stage is relatively short to have all the data-related issues defined and solved, the aim of this deliverable is to show how different data will be treated during the project.

There are three main different categories of data within the project (Figure 1).

- General Data Protection Regulation covered data:** All the needed personal data that will be collected for the project needs. Personal data must be collected according to the GDPR and the different national rules, and the data collector is responsible for its handling. These personal data cannot be shared without prior notification of the involved parties and without an agreement. Thus, this data cannot be included in the general repository and its share must be performed only in specific situations and in accordance with the regulation.
- Restricted Scope:** Data, metadata, restricted documents, and other information that is reused and generated to fulfil the developments of the different tasks but with a need for limited access. These materials should be covered by different repositories and specific rules may apply for each situation. This category allows the partners to have restricted access to specific data and metadata if needed.
- General Scope inside the Consortium:** Data, metadata, deliverables, working documents, lists of bibliographic research and common information needed for the proper development of the collaborative tasks and work of the project. All partners may have access to this data and the relevant repositories where the data will be included.
- General Scope outside the Consortium:** public deliverables, presentations in conferences, press releases, dissemination material, newsletter, etc. may be available for the general society through CAPTUS’s webpage, CORDIS or any other public repository.

Figure 1. Categories classification as function of the access and the type of repository

It is important to note that, according to the open data principles, data should be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. Thus, the project partners must aim to use and generate General Scope, although different categories exist for the cases that are needed.

To collect the information for the different partners, CIRCE has translated the Horizon Europe Data

Management Plan template (it can be found at the Funding and Tender's portal from the European Commission [1] into this document and then shared with all the partners to fill and update. Once CIRCE has collected all the information, the final complete version has been prepared and stored in the project Microsoft SharePoint being the public deliverables uploaded also in the project webpage¹

When a partner needs to update the information presented (for example, if the metadata format has suffered changes for any reason, an additional standard for metadata is selected, etc.) the partner must update it and send a mail to CIRCE informing about the change.

Following this procedure, all partners will be aware at any moment of the different approaches for Data management within the CAPTUS project and the information will be updated to the latest version.

This DMP is based on the concept of FAIR data, which stands for data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, even if the access will not be always open. Following FAIR principles in data use/reuse within the consortium to complete the actions required under the Grant Agreement and facilitate reuse beyond the CAPTUS project.

Figure 2. FAIR data

1.1 OBJECTIVE AND SCOPE

The goal of this deliverable D1.2 “Data Management Plan”, carried out under Task1.3 “Quality assurance plan and project and data management plan”, is to present the data of the project from different perspectives:

1. An overview of the technical nature and use of data in CAPTUS
2. Data openness under FAIR principles in so far as is possible to maintain the commercial interests of partners and allow the use of data in further research and validation of results.

¹ <https://captusproject.eu/>

3. Compliance with GDPR obligations and any other ethical considerations

This deliverable does not seek to provide specifics for all the different data uses, data interactions, and output that could come about in the project; but should provide a distillation of the information that is of interest to a public audience.

In general, it responds to the following points:

- The types of open and non-open data that will be generated or collected by the consortium
- Data set referencing and naming
- Data set descriptions
- Standards and metadata
- Data sharing and handling during and after the end of the project
- Archiving and preservation, during and after the project end

As a minimum, the DMP will be updated prior to the periodic evaluations/assessments of the project and updated for the final review.

1.2 INTERACTIONS

The data management plan is part of the full range of deliverables under the management work plan. As it will be released publicly it is a document that can be considered in conjunction with other public deliverables; however, consortium partners can consider it in combination with other management deliverables and project documentation some of which are not public.

It is also related to a range of technical deliverables (further described along the deliverable) which throughout the project will give better insight into the details of data usage throughout the project. In general, these deliverables are public.

2 DATA SUMMARY

For those data and following the EU's guidelines regarding the DMP, this section aims to address:

- The purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project.
- Types and formats of data generated/collected by the project.
- Expected size of the data.
- Origin of the data.
- Re-use of any existing data.
- Data utility.

This section shall provide a description of those elements in order to ensure their understanding by

the partners of the consortium. At this early stage of the project, it is not yet possible to provide an estimation of the data size.

2.1 PURPOSE OF THE DATA

As stated in the introductory section, CAPTUS is a project that relies on data collection and use/reuse during the project's runtime. In order to fulfil the objectives of CAPTUS, the project team expects to be collecting data of various kinds, sizes and qualities.

Among the activities related to the project, the most relevant datasets identified so far to be examined/considered project are as below:

- Techno-economic analysis and optimization of the fuel production process
- Optimization of the CSAR unit
- Communication and dissemination statistics
- Electrode composition/fabrication and cell architecture at different scales
- DNA sequences analysis, GC-MS lipid profiles and OD microbial cell growth
- Physicochemical properties and chemical composition of feed and upgraded fuel products
- Information on the product yields in hydrotreatment processes
- LCA, LCC, e-LCA
- Use CO₂ captured from a effluent stream of a chemical industry to produce microalgae.
- Demonstrate the feasibility to use CO₂ captured from a effluent stream of a chemical industry to produce microalgae
- HTL processing for biooil production.
- Replication potential for business case
- Mapping of renewable curtailments and its potential impact on EILs
- Characterization of CAPTUS demsites and identification of opportunities.
- Evaluate the impact of the scaled technologies under real industrial operation
- Use CO₂ captured from a effluent stream of a chemical industry to produce microalgae
- Utilities for D2 instalation

This is a non-exhaustive list and will certainly be extended in the project's runtime. Apart from them, in relation to the execution of the demonstration activities, a series of data (questionnaires, surveys, etc.) will be made available in the project, such as, in the field of dissemination and communication, reports, articles, and any other publicly available communications. Finally, within the consortium, a wide range of data is shared for management purposes, from emails to financial reporting data. Of course, most of these management-related activities are confidential and closed, available only to the specific parties involved. Any sensitive and/or confidential information about individuals and companies gathered in the CAPTUS activities will be dealt in accordance with data privacy laws and within the boundaries of the CAPTUS Grant Agreement as well as the Consortium Agreement.

From the brief presentation, it is evident that a series of data will be made available in the project. Towards this direction, the details on the way CAPTUS partners plan to manage the different datasets in the project are provided (following the template provided by EC) in the following sections.

2.2 TYPES, FORMATS AND SIZE

As stated in the introductory section, the CAPTUS project covers many activities with varied data needs across the different demonstrators, such as relevant statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images, deliverables, publications, etc. In addition, data will be reused if derived from other sources (old projects, public sources, etc.) or generated by the project partners (using measurement campaigns). While the details of the data to be gathered are not clear yet, some of the types and/or formats of data to be used and/or collected in the project are identified below.

Each partner will consider the data needs of their own use and of other partners' use in the activities they lead; as well as open access and regulatory restrictions, when considering the types and formats of data to be used. In general, data should be made open, unless there are specific reasons for not doing so. These reasons may be, among others, contractual, commercial, legal or simply the ones that are not of interest to other parties.

2.2.1 TYPES OF DATA

- Numerical, quantitative, data defining specific characteristics or values for variables. Either existing or generated (physical and chemical characteristics, technology, sizing, other market data, data to define existing regulatory conditions, etc.).
- Derived data, that arises from data analytics or further processing of raw data, such as that might be generated by the algorithms developed in the project, or any data processing in research or in the various data infrastructures.
- Qualitative data relating to results of/and project activities, like research data, surveys, questionnaires, etc.
- Project Management data, such as meeting attendance lists, contact lists, financial information, and other data on the project activities.

2.2.2 FORMATS

Where possible common formats readable with readily available software will be used. To ensure it can be easily shared and worked with by all partners involved, mainly widespread usage data types are used (for the data types as presented above) for the management activities of the project. For example:

- Microsoft Office Suite formats readable in Excel, Word, and PowerPoint (doc, .docx, .xls, .xlsx, .ppt, .pptx., etc.)

- General file types readable by a range of software (e.g. .csv, fasta, .mat, dwg, drw, dxf, .zolca and .txt)
- Document formats such as pdf for deliverables and other written documentation.
- Photographic and graphic formats readable in common software such as pdf, jpg, tiff, png, html, mp4, .vsdx, etc.
- Audio and audio-visual files in commonly readable formats.
- Other specific formats that pertain to specific software packages available for purchase.
- Other formats dictated by the data creator either within or outside the CAPTUS project such as dwg files.

Formats that are not widespread or not supported by commonly available software should be avoided if possible. Where unavoidable an attempt should be made to facilitate their reuse within the project and by professional groups if they are open data sets of interest to that wider public.

Where data is generated/collected, it should use a common data format, as described above or other accessible data format.

Data generated by and/or for specific existing software packages or tools created within the project will, where possible, be in a standard format that is readable by excel or other common basic data analytics software, especially where the tool or software is being created within the project. Currently dwg, csv and drw files are expected. Of course, some proprietary software used by partners during project activities may have a software specific format, open for users of that software package. For generated data to be accessible it must be labelled logically and clearly with sufficient detail to identify the units, source etc. This requires careful labelling of columns and naming of data archives. If calculations on said data are carried out in a data archive and are deemed accessible, then they should be sufficiently explained to be obvious to a suitably qualified third party without interrogation of the underlying operations. This requires a sufficiently detailed explanation of the underlying operations used in the data archive. In general, any data set generated/collected through the CAPTUS project should be thoroughly described, including the following information as required:

- Definition of the purpose of the data, providing a unique dataset ID
- Description of the relation to the objectives of the project
- Detail on the types and formats of data collected/generated
- Specify if existing data is being re-used (if any)
- The identification of the re-used data with an identifier
- State the origin of the data.
- State the expected data size (if known)
- Outline the data utility: to whom will it be useful.
- Provide the data privacy characterization (public or confidential)
- Identify the need for anonymization (where applicable)

2.2.3 EXPECTED SIZE OF THE DATA

Project data is generally foreseen to be of a manageable size. Access to useful data outputs will be possible with a normal PC and in some cases mobile devices. For that, data generated by the project activities (deliverables, communication material, reports) will be stored in Microsoft SharePoint as the internal repository of the project as well as to additional repositories based on access rights (i.e., project portal for public deliverables, etc....).

Regarding the size of these data, a maximum size will be set (at 15 MB) in order to not generate conflicts with emails recipients nevertheless the SharePoint can handle larger files where they may be required. For videos and moving images the 15Mb limit may not be able to be respected but they will be in the order of Mb and shareable through cloud facilities. However, in general, file sizes that are as small as possible for the intended use will be preferred.

2.3 ORIGIN OF THE DATA COLLECTION

CAPTUS aims to make use of as much previous research effort, existing literature and experiences as possible. Moreover, during the execution of the project, partners will generate their own data.

2.4 RE-USE EXISTING DATA

Apart from the data to be generated within the context of the project, additional data already available will be reused. Much data is sourced from various existing open and/or closed, private and/or public databases, such as information, results and know-how for modelling and optimal operation, for developing electrochemical processes for CO₂ conversion to produce formic acid/formate and for detailed characterization and upgrading of renewable feedstocks into clear and more sustainable fuels at lab and pilot scale among others. Or simply referencing and use of existing academic publications, standards, and knowledge or techniques. Other existing data has its origin within the different consortium partners, where the data can come from previous research including from publicly funded projects or other research data. Nevertheless, the identification by the consortium partners based on the business needs and priorities is still in process. Sources such as projects under execution or finished, bibliographical data from scientific papers and other well-known public sources are going to be used under the scope of the project. A further elaboration of the datasets to be re-used will be made available as the project evolves.

2.5 DATA UTILITY

During and after the project, the data outputs of the project may be used to disseminate the results to many different stakeholders. As target groups for the different innovations of the CAPTUS project, the following list of stakeholders and external groups may be interested in the data generated during the project:

- Energy-intensive industries (food, pulp and paper, basic chemicals, refining, iron and steel, nonferrous metals or non-metallic minerals industries) and technology providers

- RES promoters, operators and associations (EUREC, WindEurope, SolarPower Europe, EREC), DSOs (E:DSO) and TSOs (ENTSO-E)
- Factory managers, workers, bankers, insurers, investors, business developers
- EC, EU Parliament, City and regional authorities, EU policy and decision-makers, innovation and policy advisors
- ZWE, EPRO, PRE, EPRO, EERA, PRE, EPRC
- Neighborhood clusters, consumer organizations, environmental associations, students & teachers
- European Associations, International Associations and initiatives, Processes4Planet, SPIRE, EUREC, EASE, ENTSO-E, IEA, ETIP-SNET, EERA
- EU Citizen. Science, schools, students & teachers, councils and other local bodies, EC and EC services, non-expert magazines

It is evident that there is a wider interest in the results generated from the project and thus, where possible and practical, the project partners must aim to adopt the FAIR principles and aim to open and make available data and results of interest and use, for professionals for research, investigation, planning, etc. As the project progresses and the focus of exploitation becomes more evident, the data and findings will be updated furthering the exploitation aims of the partners.

3 FAIR DATA (DATA THAT IS FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSABLE)

Most of the questions that come in this section deal with specific cases. Thus, within this subsection general information and recommendations for partners are provided. Specific points will be collected in the living-working approach document as stated in the first section of this document.

3.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE

In creating FAIR digital resources, consistent data, that is persistent and with unique identifiers is needed. Towards this direction, a series of actions should be considered for creating findable data:

- Define the way the data can be discovered (including metadata provisions)
- Define the way the data can be identified by referring to a standard identification mechanism.
- Define the way naming conventions shall be used.
- Define the way method towards searching keywords.
- Define the way for versioning control.
- Define the way the standards for metadata generation (if any).

The details of the different steps are presented below.

3.1.1 DATA IDENTIFICATION AND NAMING

Data findability can be greatly enhanced following a consistent set of naming conventions. Because of this, CAPTUS creates consistent data file names that provide clues to their content, status and versioning, while also increasing their discoverability. In doing so, project partners as well as interested stakeholders can easily identify a file as well as classify and sort it.

The best practice in naming convention, is to create brief but meaningful names for data files, that facilitate classification. The naming convention should avoid the utilisation of spaces, dots and special characters (such as & or !), whereas the use of underscores is endorsed, to separate elements in the data file name and make them understandable. At the same time, versioning should be a part of a naming convention to clearly identify the changes and edits in a file. Indicatively, a naming convention for the datasets is made available in the project as follows:

- WP number associated with the dataset.

- Acronym of the partner responsible for creating/collecting and managing the dataset, specifically the same acronym as presented in the Grant Agreement.
- Descriptive data set name.
- Numerical data set sub-index (starting from 1) so as to identify data sets created/collected at different times with individual metadata.

The proposed format to be followed for naming the data sets (enabling that way the identification of the data sets internally and when published as open dataset) and a naming example is shown below:

CAPTUS_[Wpnumber]_[Responsible_Partner]_[Description]_[Data_set_Sub_Index]

Example: CAPTUS_WP10_IIAP_value chain_5

A similar process will be followed for deliverables. These files should have an alphanumeric code included in the name which identifies the version number and date of creation of the version.

CAPTUS_DX.X [Name of the deliverable]_[Responsible Partner]

Example: CAPTUS_D1.2 Data Management Plan_CIRCE

When possible, Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be used to identify content and provide a persistent link to its location on the Internet. DOI is a unique alphanumeric string assigned by a registration agency (the International DOI Foundation). The publisher assigns a DOI when an article is published and made available electronically.

The DOI is typically located on the first page of the electronic journal article, near the copyright notice. The DOI can also be found on the database landing page for the article. The DOI system has been standardised through the International Standards Organisation, ISO (within the responsibility of committee ISO TC46/SC9, Identification and documentation) as ISO 26324, Digital Object Identifier System.

All DOI numbers begin with a 10 and contain a prefix and a suffix separated by a slash. The prefix is a unique number of four or more digits assigned to organizations; the suffix is assigned by the publisher and was designed to be flexible with publisher identification standards.

3.1.2 KEYWORD

In general, keywords are a subset of metadata and include words and phrases used to name data.

In the context of CAPTUS, keywords should be used to add valuable information to the data collected/generated as well as to facilitate the description and interpretation of its content and value. Along these lines, the project's strategy on keywords is underpinned by the following principles:

- The who, the what, the when, the where, and the why should be covered.
- Consistency among the different keyword tags needs to be ensured.
- Relevant, understandable, and clear keywording ought to be sought.

The keywords must accurately reflect the content of the datasets and avoid words used only once or twice within them.

When possible, deliverable that produces core output will be tagged with keywords following the JEL Classification System (<https://www.aeaweb.org/econlit/jelCodes.php>). Moreover, all the scientific papers that will be produced during the execution of the project will include a list of keywords that will make easy their search.

3.1.3 METADATA GENERATION

In creating FAIR digital resources, metadata can (and should) be generous and extensive, including descriptive information about the context, quality and condition, or characteristics of the data. The definition of metadata should obviously be relevant to the specific data sets used/generated by consortium members for their different project tasks.

For this reason, the creation of metadata is considered as a good practice within the CAPTUS project. Metadata should include the following information:

- Datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo)
- Horizon Europe
- CAPTUS (101118265)
- Licensing terms of the data
- Persistent identifiers for the dataset
- Authors involved in the action, and, if possible, their organisations

Examples of metadata standards can be found in the reference [2]. Metadata is usually presented in two formats – contextual information about the data in a text-based document and ISO 19115 standard metadata in an xml file. These two formats for metadata provide a full explanation of the data (text format) and ensure compatibility with international standards (.xml format).

3.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

Following accessibility principles in the CAPTUS project, it is important to define which data will be made openly available and, if some datasets remain closed, the reasons for not giving access. This would define where the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited and how the data can be accessed. In any case, the project adopts the good practice namely “making data as open as possible and as closed as necessary”. This calls for project partners to disseminate the project’s data that have the potential to offer long-term value to external stakeholders and do not harm the confidentiality and privacy of the stakeholders that contributed to the collection/generation of this data, with a view to maximizing the beneficial impact of CAPTUS.

Therefore, CAPTUS partners are committed to fostering collaborative work and on a systematic sharing of knowledge and tools in the research process. CAPTUS will address this through the application of open science practices:

- **Early and open sharing of research:** In the first stage of WPs where technologies will be developed and implemented (WP2-WP6), CAPTUS partners will preregister the methodology to increase transparency about the purposes and methods of the study. This preregistration document will be posted on a publicly available website and, once the preregistered study has been conducted, a report of the study and its results will be submitted for publication together with access to the preregistration document.
- **Involvement of relevant knowledge actors, including citizens:** CAPTUS will engage the citizens and key local stakeholders through information sessions, co-creation workshops, awareness-raising campaigns, events to foster participation on the project topics and gather their main concerns in the area, providing insights for the development of CAPTUS overall solutions. Engagement and awareness creation through knowledge sharing will be key to supporting the general public in the transition from passive consumers towards active citizens.
- **Research output management and measures to ensure reproducibility of research outputs:** CAPTUS will ensure the reproducibility of the outputs by covering the three main research processes that reproducibility is based on: reproduction, replication and re-use. All these processes rest on the availability of data and methods from the original study. All the outputs of the project (data, reports, publications, etc.) will be available in Open Access repositories (being ZENODO and CORDIS the main platforms) either through preregistrations or through publications in open repositories or journals.
- **Open access to research outputs and participation in open peer-review:** A dedicated budget for open-access scientific publications is reserved. For every publication, no later than 6 months after the publication is released, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published manuscript will be available on the CAPTUS website and open-access repositories. Research data and bibliographic metadata needed to validate published results will be stored in the repository’s respective area if possible. Finally, to make project knowledge publicly available, SIG will exploit EC open-access portals and tools (e.g., OpenAIRE, Horizon the EU Research and Innovation Magazine, Research*EU Results Magazine, etc.). In any case, data related to open publications should be open to aid transparency (where making it open does not conflict with other contractual obligations), this

is also related to the obligations of the Grant Agreement. More details about scientific open access can be found in Annex II: Scientific publications handling within CAPTUS

3.2.1 REPOSITORY

The general repository for the project outcomes and work is Microsoft SharePoint and CIRCE has provided access to all partners. This repository must store information from the partners-related tasks such as: draft versions of reports, data for the work, bibliographic information, etc. The information available in this SharePoint will be accessible to all partners. In addition to the project's internal repository, additional repositories are considered under the FAIR principles.

The publicly available reports and other documents related to the project will be accessible from the CAPTUS project website (<https://dev.captusproject.eu/>) as well as the CORDIS results webpage (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101118265>). Moreover, to make its research data FAIR, CAPTUS partners are encouraged to use the free ZENODO repository (more information regarding ZENODO at Annex I: Tutorial on ZENODO – Open repository). A CAPTUS community will be established on the ZENODO website, where all public datasets and deliverables, as well as possible scientific publications with green open access, will be uploaded. It is also possible to allow open access through organisations' own solutions such as via direct links to papers.

3.2.2 DATA

The Consortium will do its best to make data open and accessible. Moreover, data is to be retrievable using a standard, open, free, and universally implementable method (protocol). The selected method will allow authentication and authorization, where necessary.

Moreover, metadata remains accessible, even when the data is no longer available. Data descriptions remain even if the timeline for the storage of data has passed.

If needed, the point of a data access committee will be discussed in the General Assembly meetings and the conclusions presented in its minutes.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data if the achievement of the action's main objective (as described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement) would be jeopardized by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.

Following the methodology of the Open Access strategy towards defining which data are to be made openly accessible, here is presented a simple structural approach formed by a list of simple (but important) questions that must be answered to classify the different datasets or information as part of the DMP:

- **Q1:** Does a result provide significant value to others or is it necessary to understand a scientific conclusion?
 - If Yes, then the result is classified as public (i.e., granted for open access). If the answer to Q1 is No, the result is classified as non-public. For example, code that is

very specific to a platform (e.g., a database initialization) is usually of no scientific interest to anyone, nor does it add any significant contribution.

- **Q2:** Does a result include personal information that is not the author's name?
 - If Q2 is answered with Yes, the result is classified as non-public. Any personal information further than the name must be removed if it should be published according to the ethics management plan of the project.
- **Q3:** Does a result allow the identification of individuals even without the name?
 - If Q3 is answered with Yes, the result is classified as non-public.
- **Q4:** Can a result be abused for a purpose that is undesired by society in general or contradicts societal norms and the project's ethics?
 - If Q4 is answered with Yes, the result should be classified as non-public. This is also managed by the ethics management plan of the project.
- **Q5:** Does a result include business or trade secrets of one or more partners of the project?
 - If Q5 is answered with Yes, the result should be classified as non-public. Any business or trade secrets need to be deleted in accordance with all partners' requirements prior to being published.
- **Q6:** Does a result name technology that consists of an ongoing, project-related patent application?
 - If Q6 is answered with Yes, the result should be classified as non-public. The result can be published once a patent has been filed.
- **Q7:** Does a result break security interests for any project partner?
 - If Q7 is answered with Yes, the result should be classified as non-public.

More details about open access for Scientific publications can be found in Annex II: Scientific publications handling within CAPTUS.

In any case, it is important to point out that CAPTUS partners are obliged to comply with the Annex V of the Grant Agreement, when referring to Open Science.

3.2.3 METADATA

Metadata are valuable in/and of themselves, when planning research, especially replication studies.

Even if the original data is missing, tracking down people, institutions or publications associated with the original research can be extremely useful. For this reason, all the partners are encouraged to prepare metadata and make it publicly available. Metadata should be stored in the general repository or even if considered as a good practice, made publicly available by means of the project webpage, or open-access repositories such as ZENODO.

For general purposes, data and metadata stored in the SharePoint of the project will remain available for one (1) extra year and for four (4) additional ones CIRCE will store them and provided them to partners under request.

The project website and the materials stored on it will be available and active for two (2) years after the end of the project.

Considering the utilization of external repositories (CORDIS, ZENODO, etc.) the data/metadata that could be open at that stage will be made available after the end of the project for further use. There are no specific limitations about the period data will be made available and findable.

Other specific situations need to be studied in detail. Nevertheless, according to the Grant Agreement Data Sheet, five (5) years are expected according to the record-keeping obligation.

As a good practice, the partners should create the needed reference documentation when needed.

3.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

Following the interoperability principles in the CAPTUS project, it is crucial to predefine which standard or field-specific data and metadata vocabularies and methods will be used during the data generation within the project. That is, the data produced and/or generated allows data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organizations, countries, etc. (i.e., adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (meaning open) software applications and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins).

In order to be interoperable, (meta)data must use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles and include qualified references to other (meta)data.

Though it is not the intention of the project to utilize uncommon data models or generate project-specific ontologies or vocabularies (as the overall concept behind the definition of the common information model of the project is to provide mappings to already existing models or ontologies) the consortium is committed to make (at the maximum level) the project specific information model specifications publicly available for further re-use.

In this sense, standard vocabularies for all data types will be present in the data set, allowing interdisciplinary interoperability. For example, when an acronym is used for the first time, an explanation between brackets will be drafted.

Besides, every deliverable includes a list of acronyms and abbreviations in which all necessary definitions guarantee proper interoperability among users and consumers.

The following typographic conventions are used in this specification:

- 1) A variable in pseudo-code or in an algorithm description is in italics (variable).
- 2) A definition of a term, to be used elsewhere in this or other specifications, is in bold and italics (definition)

- 3) A reference to a definition in this document is underlined and is also an active link to the definition itself (definition reference)
- 4) A reference to a definition in this document, when the reference itself is also a markup, is underlined, red-orange monospace font, and is also an active link to the definition itself (markup definition reference)
- 5) A hyperlink is underlined and in blue (hyperlink).
- 6) A document reference (normative or informative) is numbered in order of appearance, enclosed in square brackets and linked to the references section [reference].
- 7) The consortium will ensure that references to other data from the project or datasets from previous research (if available) will be explicitly stated.

3.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE

In order to be reusable, meta(data) must have a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes, be released with a clear and accessible data usage license, be associated with their provenance and meet domain-relevant community standards.

Due to the important nature of this project, it is precisely that all generated information and data in the project can be reused at some point in further projects and experiments if the consortium agrees on that. The consortium must do its best to make a wide variety of data that will be ingested and curated available for further re-use.

For example, the use of readme files or any other documentation is recommended to the partners that generate/reuse data. However, the best solution should be tailor-made thus specific solutions are expected. This readme information can be stored in the general SharePoint.

As commented above, the Consortium is not obliged to make data available but will check the data to be made available and ensure the widest possible re-use. In that case, the data will be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement.

Research publications and underlying data will be subject to a Creative Commons (CC) license, which regulates re-use. For publications, CC BY is the default license unless there are compelling reasons, such as IPR, for choosing a different license. CC BY permits re-users to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, provided that the author is credited [3]. CC BY also allows for commercial use. Licenses excluding commercial use, such as CC BY-NC and CC BY-ND, can be used for monographs and other long-text formats. As mentioned earlier, metadata of deposited publications must be open under CC 0.

Although reuse is not considered at the current stage of the project, all partners must work with the reuse of the data as a target. This is a good practice that CIRCE encourages partners to follow.

Finally, it is important to remark that is easier to reuse data sets if they are similar: same type of data, data organised in a standardised way, well-established and sustainable file formats, documentation (metadata) following a common template and using a common vocabulary. If community standards

or best practices for data archiving and sharing exist, they should be followed.

4 OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Each different research output should be studied in detail, as far as it can be an exploitable result. Since the nature of each of them, the storage, the tentative embargo periods, and the possibility of making it open or not should be assessed by the owner of the result.

Regarding deliverables, all the deliverables (PU and SEN) will be stored in the Microsoft SharePoint of the project. PU deliverables will also be available for the public on the project webpage and also at CORDIS once approved by the EC.

Dissemination materials will also be stored in the Microsoft SharePoint of the project.

5 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

As Coordinator of the CAPTUS Project, CIRCE is ultimately responsible for data management. Nonetheless, for the proper, effective and secure handling of the CAPTUS collected and/or generated data on the different Work Packages, the establishment of specific data management roles is required.

In this regard, responsibilities roles have been managed:

- **Project Coordinator (PC):** The PC, CIRCE, is responsible for the overall data management in the framework of CAPTUS, including the elaboration of the DMP and its updates (when necessary and with the support of all partners). At the same time, the PC is responsible for the elaboration of proper templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to be appropriately adjusted and utilized by project partners during the relevant activities of the project. Finally, the PC works closely with Work Package and Task Leaders, in order to determine whether and how the collected and/or generated data during the lifespan of the project is shared, and how it will become available for re-use.
- **Work Package Leaders (WPL):** The WPL is responsible for coordinating the implementation of the data processing activities performed under the WPs they are leading. They align with the PC and the respective Task Leader on whether and how the data gathered and/or produced under the tasks that fall within the WP they are leading will be shared and/or re-used. Finally, the WPL are the main responsible for assuring the quality of the data stemming from the activities of the WP they are leading, including assessing their quality and indicating any need for improvement to the respective Task Leaders.

Regarding the costs related to make data FAIR in the project as well as open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe Grant, as long as they are compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions. The estimation of the costs for the Microsoft SharePoint is not included here.

All partners are expected to use their own repositories and to store copies of the data after the project execution, maintaining at the same time the confidentiality and not disclosing any information. More specific discussions will take place by the whole consortium during General Assembly meetings as the data value and reuse potential becomes clearer.

The Microsoft SharePoint will be accessible to all partners for one year after the end of the project. After that period, CIRCE will store the data that has been included in the SharePoint for 4 additional years, and the access will be provided if needed prior to the request.

6 DATA SECURITY

CAPTUS aims to guarantee the findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability of the produced data during and beyond the project.

During the project's lifetime, all documents will be stored in the project's intranet (Microsoft SharePoint) guaranteeing the access of all consortium members and the recovery in case a technical issue with the public repository (website) appears. The online repository used by the consortium such as Microsoft SharePoint also have user access control and anyway is for sharing of data that can be viewed by all CAPTUS project partners, not confidential for the partners. In partners' own organizations user access control should also apply to all CAPTUS project data. These measures should help prevent unauthorized access to CAPTUS data. Backups of data will also be used across these platforms and developed infrastructures to ensure data retrieval in the case of loss. Data destruction techniques when used with the tools and infrastructures, must be permanent and irreversible, the method depending on the medium. Besides, the coordinator, CIRCE, will keep a copy of all documentation, when possible, during and beyond the project's lifetime.

Nonetheless, all project partners are responsible for data being processed within their private servers and will ensure that this data is protected, and any necessary data security controls have been implemented in order to minimize the risk of information leak and destruction.

Regarding confidential data, this type of data refers to the data that will be closed and thus, will not be shared as stated in the article 10: Non-disclosure of information, signed by the CAPTUS Consortium on the Consortium Agreement. When gathering data, especially when it is considered private under GDPR or otherwise confidential, the minimum amount of data required in order to perform the activities should be gathered. This helps data security by limiting sensitive and commercial data in storage to the minimum. Additionally, if confidential data needs to be shared, the minimum data required for the purposes of the activity should be shared. At the end of the project, the consortium will decide if long-term preservation of the data is required.

It is worth mentioning that, between industrial partners and technological partners, an NDA may also be signed in order to protect any confidential information any partner would like to protect.

Finally, as explained before, public results are set to be stored in a public (e.g., ZENODO) repository and properly standardised following the FAIR principles.

7 ETHICS

Ethical aspects are also a key point of the DMP, especially related to personal data. The collection and/or generation of data from individuals participating in the project's activities is based upon a process of informed consent. Any personal data collected and/or generated in the framework of CAPTUS is processed according to the principles laid out by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 as stated in the article 15 of the Grant Agreement on GDPR:

“ARTICLE 15 — DATA PROTECTION

15.1 Data processing by the granting authority

Any personal data under the Agreement will be processed under the responsibility of the data controller of the granting authority in accordance with and for the purposes set out in the Portal Privacy Statement.

For grants where the granting authority is the European Commission, an EU regulatory or executive agency, joint undertaking or other EU body, the processing will be subject to Regulation 2018/17251

15.2 Data processing by the beneficiaries

The beneficiaries must process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/6792).

They must ensure that personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects*
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes*
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date*
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and*
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.*

The beneficiaries may grant their personnel access to personal data only if it is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the Agreement. The beneficiaries must ensure that the personnel is under a confidentiality obligation.

The beneficiaries must inform the persons whose data are transferred to the granting authority and provide them with the Portal Privacy Statement.”

Added to the previous points, the Consortium Agreement stated the following conditions regarding

the data protection.

“4.4 Specific responsibilities regarding data protection

Where necessary, the Parties shall cooperate in order to enable one another to fulfil legal obligations arising under applicable data protection laws (the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and relevant national data protection law applicable to said Party) within the scope of the performance and administration of the Project and of this Consortium Agreement.

In particular, the Parties shall, where necessary, conclude a separate data processing, data sharing and/or joint controller agreement before any data processing or data sharing takes place.”

The Consortium partners will ensure compliance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) and its application at the national and regional level in the member states involved in the CAPTUS project. All partners directly involved with the use of personal data have prior experience and expertise sufficient to carry out the activities of the project in compliance with GDPR.

In the field of the dissemination activities of the project and the usage of personal data, GEO as Communication and Dissemination leader and CIRCE as coordinator and responsible for webpage may collect the following information:

- Mail
- Name
- Organisation
- Country
- Other personal data of interest

CIRCE and GEO will store the data for dissemination purposes and this data will not be shared without written notice. Moreover, GEO and CIRCE will store the data, as Figure 1. Categories classification as function of the access and the type of repository has presented, in a separate repository. The data collection is made by means of a form on the CAPTUS webpage, registration to events, etc.

Therefore, collected data will be used exclusively within the context and for the purpose of the CAPTUS project. No data will be transmitted to any person, company or organization not involved in the CAPTUS project. Collected data will not be used for commercial purposes and participation will happen on a voluntary basis.

All personal data will be collected, stored and destroyed only with and accordingly to the consent of the personal data holder. Necessary measures will be taken to guarantee optimal anonymization of the collected, analysed and stored data. Respondents will be comprehensibly informed about it. Whenever necessary, survey respondents will be requested for their explicit consent (e.g., in case

of follow-up/second-layer contacts & questionnaires).

The CAPTUS project partners will adopt a data minimisation policy at all levels of the project.

8 OTHER ISSUES

At the current stage of the project the usage of any other procedure for data management is not foreseen.

9 CONCLUSIONS

As has been stated, this document is the first version of the Data Management Plan. The aim of this report is to collect, process, and synthesize which methodology and standards will be applied during data collection and handling, elaborate procedures for sharing information and for open access of the CAPTUS data and explain how to curate and preserve the data.

This DMP also sets the procedures for the sharing of data of the project, addressing the FAIR principle, making the research data Findable, openly Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

The plan also takes into account some key points such as allocations of resources, data security or ethical aspects.

The plan can be considered as a checklist for the future and as a reference for the resource and budget allocations related to data management.

It is also important to highlight that the DMP is intended to be a living document in which information can be updated as the implementation of the project progresses and when significant changes occur.

10 REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission, „Data Management,“ 2016.
- [2] Enlightenbio, „FAIR Data or the Journey Towards Data-Centricity – Pushing Towards Making Data Discoverable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable,“ 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://enlightenbio.com/news-and-features/2021/05/06/fair-data-or-the-journey-towards-data-centricity-pushing-towards-making-data-discoverable-accessible-interoperable-and-reusable/>.
- [3] University of Bath, „Metadata Standards Catalogue,“ 2023.

11 ANNEXES

11.1 ANNEX I: TUTORIAL ON ZENODO – OPEN REPOSITORY

ZENODO is a multidisciplinary, open repository for educational material, research papers, data, and reports. Developed under the European OpenAIRE program, ZENODO is operated by CERN to support the principles of FAIR data. It allows the uploads to be citable and trackable through DOI, the uploading process is fast, the datasets can be updated with a versioning feature, the uploads provide usage statistics, and its GitHub integration allows for preserving GitHub repositories.

ZENODO generally accepts datasets up to 50 GB; however, larger datasets may be accepted under special circumstances. At present, there are no limits on the number of datasets per community, so there will not be any additional costs associated with making data FAIR through ZENODO.

Moreover, ZENODO will be used to store metadata of the publications and datasets. Metadata associated with each published dataset in ZENODO will include:

- Digital Object Identifiers (DOI)
- Abstract/description
- File sizes
- Keywords
- Related identifiers
- Version numbers
- Associated project and community
- Associated publications and reports
- Access and licensing info
- Language
- Grant agreement number
- Specific keywords

Rich metadata enhances the discoverability of data. Using JSON Schema as the internal representation of metadata, ZENODO offers export to other popular formats, such as Dublin Core and MARCXML. The metadata in ZENODO is openly available under the CC 0 license, which complies with the requirements of the European Commission.

The portal enables researchers, scientists and institutions to share research data and results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio and video. To each submitted dataset is attached a unique DOI that enables referencing the data in research and institutional contexts. The OpenAIRE project, in the vanguard of the open access and open data movements in Europe was commissioned by the EC to support their nascent Open Data policy by providing a catch-all repository for EC-funded research.

The submission of research data to ZENODO can be done through the following steps:

1. The upload procedure starts by prompting the user to select the files that will be part of the dataset and need to be uploaded:

The screenshot shows the ZENODO user interface for a new upload. The top navigation bar is blue and contains the ZENODO logo, a search bar, and links for 'Upload' and 'Communities'. A user profile 'mlanero@fcirce.es' is displayed on the right. Below the navigation bar is a search bar for uploads and a green 'New Upload' button. The main content area features a large 'Get started!' heading, a sub-heading 'Make your first upload - all research outputs from across all fields of research are welcome.', and a prominent green 'New upload' button. The footer contains navigation links, funding logos (CERN, OpenAIRE, EU), and status information.

Figure 3. ZENODO submission process. New upload

2. Successively the data must be classified according to given categories such as: dataset (i.e., tables of numerical data), image and others:

Figure 4. ZENODO submission process. Classification

3. Finally, the portal prompts for additional metadata such as authorship of data and sharing policies. The structure of the dataset must be specified here as well:

Basic information
required ▼

Digital Object Identifier e.g. 10.1234/foo.bar

Optional. Did your publisher already assign a DOI to your upload? If not, leave the field empty and we will register a new DOI for you. A DOI allows others to easily and unambiguously cite your upload. Please note that it is NOT possible to edit a Zenodo DOI once it has been registered by us, while it is always possible to edit a custom DOI.

Reserve DOI

Publication date * 2017-10-27

Required. Format: YYYY-MM-DD. In case your upload was already published elsewhere, please use the date of first publication.

Title *

Required.

Authors *

Family name, given names

Affiliation

ORCID (e.g.: 0000-0002-1825-0097) ↕ ×

Optional.

+ Add another author

Description *

📎 📄 **B** *I* ~~S~~ ~~x₂~~ ~~x²~~ ≡ ≡ ” ↶ ↷ *I_x* Σ Ω 📄 Fuente HTML 🔄

Required.

Language

e.g.: 'eng', 'fr' or 'Polish'

Optional. Primary language of the record. Start by typing the language's common name in English, or its ISO 639 code (two or three-letter code). See [ISO 639 language codes list](#) for more information.

Keywords

↕ ×

+ Add another keyword

Additional notes

Optional.

Figure 5. ZENODO submission process. Basic information

License
required ▼

Access right *

- Open Access
- Embargoed Access
- Restricted Access
- Closed Access

Required. Open access uploads have considerably higher visibility on Zenodo.

License *

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Required. Selected license applies to all of your files displayed on the top of the form. If you want to upload some of your files under different licenses, please do so in separate uploads. If you cannot find the license you're looking for, include a relevant LICENSE file in your record and choose one of the 'Other' licenses available ('Other (Open)', 'Other (Attribution)', etc.). The supported open licenses in the list are harvested from opendefinition.org. If you think that an open license is missing from the list, please [contact us](#).

Figure 6. ZENODO submission process. License

Communities
recommended ▼

Any user can create a community collection on Zenodo ([browse communities](#)). Specify communities which you wish your upload to appear in. The owner of the community will be notified, and can either accept or reject your request.

Communities

✕

+ Add another community

Figure 7. ZENODO submission process. Communities

Funding
recommended ▼

Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via [OpenAIRE](#). Specify grants which have funded your research, and we will let your funding agency know!

Grants

European Commission (EU)

✕

Optional. OpenAIRE-supported projects only. For other funding acknowledgements, please use the *Additional Notes* field.
Note: a human Zenodo curator will need to validate your upload - you may experience a delay before it is available in OpenAIRE.

+ Add another grant

Figure 8. ZENODO submission process. Funding

11.2 ANNEX II: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS HANDLING WITHIN CAPTUS

In this section, the details about the way to handle publication dissemination in the project are provided. This information is partly extracted from the EC project portal and thus provided in the Annex for reference.

Figure 9. Open Access strategy for publications and scientific data

Open Access to scientific publications may be achieved in two ways as presented above in figure 9:

- **Self-archiving / “Green” open access:** these are the publications that can be made available in an online repository before, at the same time as, or after publication (with no extra costs required). Green open access implies no publishing costs for the project, but the final version of the article will only be available to journal subscribers. With green access, the author's version of the article (not the journal version) can be published elsewhere, in CAPTUS's case on the project website and ZENODO. Many of the major journals in the field require a 24-month embargo with green access schemes.
- **Open access publishing / “Gold” open access:** the article is immediately published in open access mode but requires a fee to be paid. In that case, the publication costs are usually covered by the entity (university, institute, etc.) funding the research. In other cases, the costs of open-access publishing are covered by subsidies or other funding models. Publishing under the gold access scheme typically costs between 2 000€ and 3 000€ per article. But it is important to remark that this cost is only accepted within Horizon Europe rules in “full open access publishing venues”. Gold access will be preferred within the limits of the project budget.

To comply with the open access principles, CAPTUS will apply a hybrid of gold and green access schemes. Choosing the scheme will be determined by the project coordinator, the dissemination lead, and the partners concerned on a case-by-case basis.

The project target is to publish at least 8 peer-reviewed papers and a dedicated budget for open-

access scientific publications is reserved in the project. However, if the budget is inadequate – and to allocate the dissemination resources effectively – gold access should be used on a discretionary basis for each publication.

According to the Consortium Agreement signed by the partners article 8.4.2

“8.4.2 Dissemination of own (including jointly owned) Results

8.4.2.1

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17.4 of the Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section Dissemination, subject to the following provisions.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 30 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted, in accordance with the notice given.”

Thus, prior to any publication all the involved parties, CIRCE as coordinator and GEO must be notified to ensure that the process is followed accordingly.